

Preliminary Note About the Transcription

This document reports the focus group interview performed to validate the results presented in Bertrand, Y., Schultheis, A., Malburg., L, Grueger, J., Serral Asensio, E., Bergmann, R. Challenges in Data Quality Management for IoT-Enhanced Event Logs, accepted at the RCIS conference 2025.

The transcript has been prepared verbatim, but obvious repetitions of words, slips of the tongue and minor grammatical errors have been corrected to improve readability. No changes were made to the content or semantics. Irrelevant parts such as the greeting, technical problems (e.g. because of non-functioning microphones), or off-topic comments have been removed. The names of the speakers have been anonymized to protect their privacy.

Transcript

[Welcome]

00:00:13 Interviewer

Let's start with our challenges. So, we have come up with 13 challenges which are grouped in four main groups. First, we have data type changes that pertain to the type of data. So, we are here mostly talking about sensor data. Sensor data have well some inherent issues which make it difficult to work with them. I think you all have an idea of what I'm talking about. Then we have some challenges about the knowledge that we have about data quality issues. So, how well we know these issues, how well we can identify them, makes it more or less difficult to handle them. Then there are some which are about some conflicting interests with the business, for instance. Which make that the business might not always require or desire to have the best data quality possible or might not be willing to take all the steps necessary for that. And we have some about the management of data quality or the more system limits to handle the challenges. We're presenting them in a quite arbitrary order, by the way, so it's not that the first group or the first issues are the most important. That's something that we would like to discuss with you later as well.

Presentation of Group 1 – Data Type

So, our first issue there in the data type will be the volume. Typically, if you have a process running continuously, you have multiple sensors, you will get a lot of data. Having a lot of data makes it difficult to spot potential issues and to process all the data correctly, just for computational reasons. You could try to solve that by somehow simplifying or

abstracting the data, but then you might also lose some information which is relevant. So, there might be a tradeoff here. Our second challenge is again about big data, and it's about the variety of the data. Even if we only consider sensor data, you might have different types of sensors, some of them which record some continuous measurements, some of them which are more event-based. Some of them might be contradicting each other or be more or require a different handling technique or preprocessing. They might correlate, or they might not, and you have to analyze them sometimes all together to get some relevant information, which is difficult. Then we have a third big data issue, which is the velocity. It's about how fast the data gets recorded and collected. And the fact that you have to keep up with that space in your data quality handling. Otherwise, you end up with huge batches of data which are even more difficult to handle, and sometimes you for some business needs you do in real time. So, that's on a second strain on how complex or analysis can be of the data. Then, we have the fourth challenge, which is granularity. Which is here more about how much preprocessing we might want to do on the sensor data to get them to a better abstraction level which makes it easier to spot issues or not. So, it's a bit linked with the volume where we might want to do some reprocessing, some abstraction to get less data, but then the abstracted data might make it more difficult to get more relevant information. And it is again about, do we want to analyze the sensor data as it is or abstracted? You might also relate that to whether we want to do it at the edge to simplify our life and make simple calculations or abstract it and use more complex techniques.

Presentation of Group 2 – Knowledge

Then, we have our second group of challenges which relates to the knowledge that we have of DQI. And there our first challenge will be challenge 5: new data quality issues. How can you detect some new issues which have never been observed before? How then, even if you detect them, can you propose some solution for these data quality issues? Well, you might need to ask for a human. But how will the human know? How do you know when this new data quality issue has been solved correctly? How do you know how the data should be without the issue basically? Then related to this, we have our sixth challenge, which is the slightly milder version. You have detected a new data quality issue at some point in the past that you have not observed very often. You might have some sort of gold start problem for the identification. That you have very few instances of your data which have this data quality issue and might be difficult to recognize it. And it might be a bit tricky to apply the initial solution. Maybe that you can, you still need to refine this solution or this handling process that you have applied in the first place. Then, we have two related issues about ambiguity. When you are analyzing some new data and trying to determine if there are some data quality issues. It might be difficult to classify the issue correctly, even if you know that there is one. You might have sometimes very similar effects in the sensor data for very different problems at the source. So, for instance, you could have noise in your data as mentioned here because your sensor is not

calibrated correctly. Or it could be due to some problem in the environment which generates some noise. So, the issue is how do we identify the correct cause. And then, C8 is the corollary: How do you know, then, that you're proposing the right solution? Because if you're not sure about the source, you might not be sure about what to do about it. And we have a last challenge for Group 2, which is what we call procedure refinement. If you have a system for the management of your data quality that is suggesting some solutions or some cleaning methods for your data, how do you update it? And how do you check that the solutions that you applied, the script that you executed on your data has actually cleaned the data correctly. How do you update your system if needed?

[Inquiry whether everyone can follow the content till here.]

Presentation of Group 3 – Conflict of Interest

Then we have Group 3, which we call the conflict of interest, where we have first the issue of privacy. So here the thing is, that it's typically better to share data to construct a new system because then you have a wider / broader training set. You have seen more types of issues, and you can train your system to make it more robust. But typically, especially if data has to be shared between different companies, even though sometimes within certain organizations, it can be very difficult to share data. Well, people don't like to share data, they like to keep their data. Sometimes you actually need / you actually have privacy issues if you have data about people who were handling your process, for instance. So, here the issue is, it would be to share data, but it's typically something that people don't want to do. Then we have our challenge 11, which is business interest conflicts. Here, the thing is, data quality is typically / should be determined by the business. So, the business should tell you which kind of issues in your data are actually problematic and which ones can then be left in your data. Sometimes you might have, for instance, a sensor that's broken, which is obviously causing data quality issues because then either your data is not correct or they're missing. But it might be from an economic point of view better to leave it as it. Because the cost of replacement is too high, or you might simply have to execute your process for some time while the new part or the new sensor arrives. So sometimes you might have data quality issues which could be avoided, but where the cost in the economic sense would be too high. Or in instances where the data quality problem is not very bad and not impacting the analysis a lot. You might have some business pressure to leave it as it is. While this is obviously well, hampering the quality of your data. And then we come to C12, which is a rather specific issue of data quality issues cascade where sometimes some early issue in the process or in the data collection is causing the process to make wrong decisions or to execute incorrectly and causes problems later, in which case solving the data quality issue will afterward result in a completely nonsensical process execution because then you won't be able to understand why things have gone wrong. Because you have solved the issue that caused all the rest and analysis of this process instance or this activity will not make any sense. For instance, here we have this example that a light barrier would not be working while a

workpiece is passing through it. The process would not detect the workpiece. If you have a robot that's supposed to grip the piece, it would not pick it up. And the workpiece would not be transported any further. But if you repair your data quality issue about the light barrier saying "Okay, actually the workpiece pass through the light barrier" at that point, then the rest of the process makes no sense. You might conclude that your Gripper robot is not working correctly what it does, but it did not pick the piece because of the earlier problem.

Presentation of Group 4 – Data Quality Management

And here, we get into our fourth group of challenges, which is about the management of data quality. Where we have two main issues, the representation of knowledge. So, the knowledge of people about the data quality types that exist and about the solutions that can be applied to them. How can you represent this knowledge in a suitable way? So that, on the one hand, other people understand it, and you could automatically reuse that knowledge. For instance, if some people, some data engineer knows that if you have one specific sensor which is not working properly, you just need to apply a certain script and that will clean the data and make it usable again. How do you integrate this data, or how do you make it so that it's clear that you just have to apply this script in this kind of issue? Or it could be on the other hand, that some engineers know very well that sometimes one sensor is not working correctly, or one sensor is somehow uncalibrated quite often, and has to be recalibrated often. How do you make sure that this knowledge can be shared or can be represented suitably in your system so that others can learn from it, or at least apply the same techniques? C14 is about the reuse and the transfer. So, when it has been represented suitably this knowledge, how can you maybe reuse it across other production lines or across other people? And how can you try to generalize it to other similar issues? So, that was our last challenge. Do you have any questions about the things that I just presented? Or was everything crystal clear?

00:15:27 Speaker 2

So, to me, it was quite clear. Are we supposed to discuss still after some further input from you? Or is it now the moment for that?

00:15:37 Interviewer

First, I would like to give you a few more specific questions so that you can start from that. I was just asking if everything was clear and showing you everything back so that you know. But OK, if then if everything is perfectly clear.

00:16:01 Speaker 3

I maybe have a question to C12. If you maybe could more define what repair in your example means. Like if you take the example, what exactly would you repair in the log?

00:16:22 Interviewer

And you mean here? [Points at statement "*Repairing the event log would no longer reflect the logic of the process.*"]

00:16:26 Speaker 3

Yes.

00:16:28 Interviewer

In the example, the initial issue was that you had missing sensor data that you did not record that work piece went through a light barrier. So, this would be the thing that has to be repaired here. Another thing is, if you repair the data to add this missing event from the light barrier, then the rest of the process doesn't really make sense because then, well, then it's more difficult to understand why the group robot did not pick up the workpiece. Because in your data, it shows you should have seen it, and then you might conclude that your group of robots is having problems while the initial issue was not there.

00:17:21 Speaker 3

OK. Thanks.

00:17:25 Speaker 4

Can you provide some more access to the slides that you have. So, we can maybe look them up again? I don't remember everything.

[*Slides were sent to participants via PDF.*]

00:17:39 Speaker 5

Maybe one question from me. So, these are challenges regarding data quality or analysis of data?

00:17:47 Interviewer

Data quality. So, the quality of the data and at the same time typically mean issues during analysis. Here, we wanted to give the example to also show why it was an issue.

00:18:05 Speaker 5

OK. And so, I don't know, for example, privacy would then also be an issue during analysis because data would be missing, or?

00:18:16 Interviewer

It could be this, but it's also more about the creation of your system to handle data quality that privacy might make it make some data quality issues unavailable to you, for training, for instance, of your system, which you might then later encounter, and which you might have more difficulty identifying and handling. Because, for instance, another plant which has a very similar production process did not share their data. You did not see that they sometimes had issues with a specific type of sensor, or a machine which was not recording data correctly. Because of, well, you could have if you had this data, it would have been easier for you to handle the same types of issues and not having it, makes it more difficult.

[Discussion about problems with the PDF file.]

00:22:38 Interviewer

Then we have four main discussion points for you. Which are

- 1) First, are there for you challenges that are missing? Or are there some challenges which you think are super fluid and should be removed?
- 2) Would you want to combine some challenges, or do you think that some of them should actually be split up into more specific problems?
- 3) Which of these challenges have you encountered in your work or in your experience? And do you have some examples?
- 4) And finally, we would also like to have your idea on which of these challenges are the most important, which ones are less important? Either from a group of challenges perspective or from individual challenges which you think are more or less problematic.

So, these are our 4 main issues. So, let's start with: Are there things for you missing, or are there things which actually are not really problematic?

00:24:00 Speaker 4

So, what about issues in metadata? Have you also thought about those, so, like insufficient information about sensor?

00:24:11 Interviewer

That's a good point. It's not something that we have really here.

00:24:21 Speaker 4

This is something that I've at least encountered that I get some readings, but I don't probably know everything about them. I probably don't know what they mean.

00:24:33 Interviewer

I think it's somehow related to the second group of issues there, but at the same time it's something a little bit different. So, go on.

00:24:52 Speaker 3

There are also some areas of compliance where you need to provide certain granularity of information. We had that when measuring testable levels in events, when technology like sound, where we need to provide a certain kind of clarity over the course of the evening to ensure that we're not higher than 95 degrees over 30 seconds.

00:25:23 Interviewer

I think it's a very nice example of granularity constraints. I don't think it's another type of issue, but it's a nice example.

00:25:43 Speaker 2

I have more of a question. So, when you started with Group 1, you triggered my memories of the four VS of data quality and big data, right? And of course, this is not the one that

would fit in your Group 1, but the veracity is the fourth V that we are missing here. So, would you place it in the knowledge, and would you position it as somewhat cross challenge across let's say C5, C6, C7, for example? Did you consider this aspect?

00:26:22 Interviewer

Not really, because typically, we assume that data comes from a trustworthy source. So, you don't really have to check whether the data is true or not. But I guess data quality is also somehow veracity of the data in the sense that can you trust that the data is correct or not?

00:26:47 Speaker 2

Yeah, and therefore, I would honestly miss that. Probably I would see it in Group 2. I can see that to some extent this is somewhat subsumed by a few of these challenges that you have there, as you mentioned, but maybe this is something that would require, in my opinion, some further investigation.

00:27:15 Interviewer

OK.

00:27:16 Speaker 3

I'm not sure if it belongs to group 2 or 4. But do you also maybe need to check if existing knowledge is still relevant if you switch sensors more often, maybe switch brands? That existing knowledge - because you have this like C5 and C6 where, so you say new data issues or rare data quality issues - is still relevant when switch or sensor happens on anything else.

00:27:54 Interviewer

You mean that C14, for instance, is especially a problem if you have new issues where you might need some transfer or some reuse of knowledge? And you might be less of an issue if you are able to represent and share your knowledge more easily?

00:28:14 Speaker 3

That on the one hand, but maybe also if you have like a data quality issue that you don't get or that you have a lot of outliers and with a new sensor, this doesn't happen anymore, but you still check your data for it. In this case, it maybe would make no sense, but in other scenarios or other sensor types that maybe really fluctuate in values, then you don't have to check for this data quality issue anymore.

00:28:45 Interviewer

Sorry, can you repeat?

00:28:51 Speaker 3

I'm not sure if it's a thing. If you have a sensor who has certain problems, or a group of sensors that have a certain problem, and you find a data quality issue, and you treat your log with it, and then you switch out the sensors and over time just data quality issue does not appear anymore. Then you still check your log because of past knowledge. That you maybe need to update your knowledge base about it. That this doesn't have many more because you maybe have like this data quality issue together with metadata quality issue, which is a problem, but each single one is no problem. And if one doesn't occur anymore, then also the combination does not occur anymore. Not have a concrete example for it.

00:29:45 Interviewer

No, it seems like a very specific case and at the same time, I think it relates to C9, which was about procedure refinement. In the sense that at some point, if you repair your process or your sensor, you might not have some issue which you had earlier, and then you might have to update your system or your procedure so that it doesn't always check for it, or it doesn't flag it very often as it may be used to for good reasons earlier that doesn't need to do now.

00:30:24 Speaker 3

And also, that your knowledge base does not go bigger and bigger over time.

00:30:31 Interviewer 2

Yeah.

00:30:34 Speaker 4

How would you classify the other way around, where you see this drift due to the data quality of specific sensors? For example, declining over time? Would that be something that you consider somewhere?

00:30:50 Interviewer

I guess it would mostly be about the procedure refinement, but that's a good question because then you might need to change your solution, or your handling based on that.

00:31:05 Speaker 4

And you have to be aware of it. I mean, it's not just about doing it once, but you need to basically continuously somehow monitor the data quality and then might initiate some actions to repair. Would that fit into 9?

00:31:30 Interviewer

Somehow. But I think in that case the issue might also be that at the beginning you might just apply some script to clean the data, but in the end, you might have to take some more drastic measures or to update your script. Until at some point you eventually have to replace the sensor.

00:31:55 Speaker 4

So, it's a bit about also about some hardware issues, I guess.

00:32:01 Interviewer

Yeah, it's also maybe a little bit the C-11 because in the end, if it's the hardware issue, you could also just say let's replace it whenever it's not working properly anymore. But then you have to make a tradeoff when it is really bad enough to justify the replacement. So, I think it's also a nice example. I think you also gave a couple of nice examples of how things could interact.

00:32:30 Interviewer

That's nice.

00:32:31 Speaker 4

Yes, so I think a specific use case was often more than one challenge. Could that be, yes?

00:32:33 Interviewer

Yeah.

00:32:42 Speaker 2

Something maybe related to this to some extent comes to my mind. It's a challenge that I worked upon some years ago. It was about balancing privacy and enforceability of business decisions in business processes, meaning you have privacy issues that make it not possible for you to validate certain business decisions that were taken during the execution of a process. I think in this context this would relate more to the validation of the data. Which might be challenged by the fact that you have some privacy constraints. So you do not have access to some data that would allow you to do some validation of other data. And this is indeed a challenge. Would you consider that as part of, for example, C11? Is it something you considered?

00:33:47 Interviewer

I think we would first categorize it as part of C10, even though it definitely touches upon C 11 because yeah, I mean, then you have the cost of privacy versus the cost of, well, not having privacy. Which you have to somehow balance. So. I think it's also nice. Yeah. Example or a nice use case.

00:34:18 Speaker 2

If you want, I can point you to the paper where this was discussed.

00:34:24 Interviewer

OK.

00:34:24 Speaker 2

I would find it and share it.

00:34:31 Speaker 4

So another use case where we would just how you would categorize the issue that for example that you may have dropped? Sensor readings due to some network issues or something like that which causes issues in the data quality. How would you classify this? Or is this an issue? And how would you?

00:34:54 Interviewer

I think it's a data quality issue. And it's. Yeah, I'm not sure if it's really sorry.

00:34:58 Speaker 4

Your sources really producing the data without any issues, but then in the collection on another computer. There might appear some issues. I think this is something with volume and velocity of course, but it's not a...

00:35:20 Interviewer

I think it's a data quality issue, but it's not the worst one because you can. Well, then what you might have is like this ambiguity problem where you might think, OK, what went wrong, and then you don't really find anything that went very wrong. And the solution might not be obvious at first, or you might think, oh, maybe I have some issues with my sensor and then think about replacing it. That would be useless in that case. And the best you can do is try to impute. The missing data, I guess. So there you might have some. Yeah, some challenges. I guess you also always have the business interest conflicts of having a better network.

00:36:06 Speaker 4

Yeah, you never know.

00:36:10 Interviewer

I mean, I guess it's always possible to have a better network, but it's always more costly. So yeah. Yeah.

00:36:22 Speaker 3

Could maybe C13 be split into two parts where you have one knowledge about single entities like if you have only one sensor that can provide you with data and the second knowledge representation about the surroundings that you have. For example, in redundancy. If you have multiple sensors measuring the same that you can use other values to compensate for missing or broken values. Based on the setup.

00:36:54 Interviewer

Some information about like the correlation or about the process itself, you mean, versus some information about the sensors?

00:37:06 Speaker 3

Yeah. If you have maybe one temperature sensor, that often makes a problem and in some scenarios you only have one sensor can like measure temperature from food. But if you have two or three sensors around, then maybe you find a DQI in one sensor reading. Depends on your granularity, for sure. But you have two sensors who are in the same room who can be used instead. And the log can be fixed by just using the measures from the other sensors. But then you need some metadata. That can provide you with information about the concrete setup in the room.

00:37:44 Interviewer

I was just thinking that it made me think about the comment from Speaker 4 about metadata. And that it is.

00:37:53 Speaker 3

That's related to that. Yeah.

00:37:55 Interviewer

There might be an additional issue there which we have not really thought about yet.

00:38:06 Speaker 5

Maybe a question from my side because I think so. The Group 1 is mainly that you have too much data, right? The reasons why you have too much data and the thing. It's mainly that you have not enough or false data, so data is missing because of privacy things. Or, I don't know. And in Group 4 you have the same, but only with the metadata, right? So I think that especially for group 3 and 4, maybe there are some reasons missing because I think as Speaker 4 said, there are then sometimes where there are many reasons why data can be missing network stuff like physical sensors. I mean, if you don't have a sensor to measure something, is this a data quality issue? I don't know, probably, but in the end, everything leads to in Group 3 you have missing data which you don't have and which you also can't get, right? And I don't know if we can like to enumerate all the reasons why we would have this missing data. I think for why we have too much data. I think this is rather complete, or I can't come up with. Regarding this missing data or incorrect data, I don't know if there are, I mean, there are very many reasons for this. I don't know if you can name all of them. Because, yeah, it depends on many different things.

00:39:49 Speaker 4

But also, granularity could be the other way around. You could also have just not enough data. So the data can be too close for addition, it's not enough.

00:39:56 Speaker 5

Yeah, yeah.

00:40:07 Interviewer

That's an interesting point. I also agree with the point of Speaker 4 that granularity is not only about having a lot of data at a low granularity level. It's also about well if it's a low granularity level, you respective of the volume, you might have to do some pre-processing.

Might lead to some issues. Might make your life. Even if you have a small volume, and you might sometimes not have the right granularity if you have a temperature sensor which is measuring like just Crisp degrees. While sometimes you need some more refined information than yeah, that can also make your life more difficult. But actually, you could also say it's an inequality issue in some sense. You don't record the data at the proper granularity level. In that sense. Yeah, I also.

00:41:07 Speaker 4

Sorry if I can interrupt, I would probably call a group 1 something about heterogeneity because this is the problem, right? All of these four aspects in the same system might vary. This is what causes your problems, usually. They are not. The volume can. It's probably not the same from different sources to variety. It is not. It's kind of like little heterogeneity of all these four aspects. You will basically get, you have some challenges.

00:41:37 Interviewer

Mm. Yeah, and for group...

00:41:43 Speaker 4

Go ahead. Yeah.

00:41:46 Interviewer

The goal of the Focus group is also that you interact among yourselves, so. If I can speak less for me, it's even better. Though I wanted to say that yeah, for Group 3, it's interesting what Speaker 5 mentioned. Do you have other ideas of these things that cause some sort of missing data because of some, I would say, business pressure or some process pressure because I think that what Speaker 3 mentioned with the multiple sensors might also be a bit related?

00:42:18 Speaker 5

So, I mean, obviously sometimes you just don't have sensors at some points or some locations where you think you would need some and which if you add them, they can then perfectly explain what you're looking for. But the sensors which you have just can't. And then additionally, so at least in some machine tools, I think there is also the problem that data measurement is not their main concern. For these machine tools, it's important that they are fast or maybe not fast, but they are very precise and measuring of the data is only like a second concern. If there are operations which need much computing power in this... is it PLC? I don't know. Then sometimes the data recording is a bit delayed and only gets done as an afterthought. But I mean this is. It should be this way so. But yeah, it affects your data, obviously. They can think of many things where I mean the sensors are just working, maybe even as they are supposed to be, but they just don't record or send the data in the granularity or whatever you need. But yeah. I don't know.

00:43:53 Speaker 4

So for example, here we have if I can also just quickly jump in as another use case that we have, which probably shows the conflict of interest quite nicely, is that we have in our smart healthcare setting where we are also using different rather simple sensors to try to track what people are doing. As opposed to using cameras, for example, which is much more privacy invasive, but could be much more precise, but probably in the end more expensive to process and to buy, of course, and to operate. But this is, of course, the privacy invasive, and then we have this conflict of interest tradeoffs where we see, OK. Some things we cannot really distinguish as nicely as we would like, there are ambiguities because the sensors aren't enough. And the trade-off would be to buy cameras, be more invasive, but then be also more precise, as if you're looking for another use case this could be one.

00:44:51 Speaker 5

So you would get them like advantages in this group too with the knowledge, right? So that you know better what happens.

00:45:01 Speaker 4

So, of course, you first have to identify these issues, right? This is also something that we have in the arXiv paper. Currently, that we are basically using the method, we will identify missing sensors basically. We have to know which sensors are missing. Somehow find it out and then could think about these trade-offs and have more knowledge about the setup than in the end, yes.

00:45:26 Speaker 2

In the healthcare scenario, that could also be that we identify ambiguity rather than missing sensors because we have the data, but we are still uncertain whether to interpret it in way or the other. And then we can say, OK, we activate the camera, and we become more privacy invasive, and we can disambiguate using these additional sensors.

00:45:53 Speaker 5

So you add some sensors, let's say on the fly, if you find out that you're currently.

00:45:59 Speaker 2

Yeah, that would be the idea.

00:46:06 Interviewer 2

OK.

00:46:07 Speaker 2

So if I may challenge another aspect. I took note that C12 to me is a bit specific, but still applies kind of to all the challenges that you have there, right? So, it's more of a consequence of having some data quality issues, but then you have cascading problems. So, does that make sense to have it as one of the challenges, or is it a consequence anyway of the fact that you have a challenge?

00:46:43 Speaker 5

Think I also agree a bit with Speaker 2 that especially C1, I think, is not really on the same level, maybe as the other challenges because it just describes that many of them. It can lead to cascading effects, right?

00:47:05 Speaker 2

Yeah, suppose you have. I don't know ambiguity, once again, just because I'm familiar with the topic. We have shown in the paper that actually ambiguity leads to cascading effects. So this is kind of implicit in the fact that you have this challenge. Unless I misunderstood to some extent your definition of C12. So maybe Interviewer, you could clarify a bit on that in case.

00:47:36 Interviewer

Yeah, I think. Well, I think the issue with the cascade is that you cannot correct the DQI. Well, it's you don't correct the DQI fast enough. And because of that, the process keeps running with this issue and if you correct it afterwards. Then it's too late. So, and you have other problems which will become even more ambiguous if you have corrected the DQI than if you haven't. So maybe you could say that it's somehow. A consequence, a consequence of the velocity of the data maybe or of the delay that it takes to actually solve the issue, which, well, gives the opportunity to the original DQI to cause more problems later.

00:48:35 Speaker 2

So, isn't that the challenge of when or how timely you can address the data quality issues?

00:48:46 Speaker 3

Do you have any time frame you work in that you say we want to have a real life DQI system? Or is it everything analyzed on the logs later? Or are these challenges, especially in regard to real time?

00:49:10 Interviewer

I think most of the challenges don't really make a difference between real time or analysis later. Yeah.

00:49:24 Speaker 3

I think the whole Group 3 is hard for me to consider when having real time because also like business interest conflicts or privacy issues also are dependent if you had these examples of an AI model running over the data. Considering privacy information maybe being leaked for, then this would be a problem that maybe is worse if you don't do a good time. Also, some business interests are not known in real time. Because if you consider do we want to replace the sensor or do we want to keep it and something that does not be decided in one minute or two minutes?

00:50:17 Interviewer

Then that's true, unless you have a specific policy behind it. But yeah, even then.

00:50:21 Speaker 3

Yeah, also some privacy maybe need to be checked if it is legal or if it's not legal to leak certain information or not.

00:50:39 Interviewer

Do you think we should also consider the time aspect of all this make a difference between challenges which are worse if we are working in real time or at the later time, or at

least mention that some of them make it even more difficult to work in real time or some of them are solved if you work in real time or something like that.

00:51:04 Speaker 3

Maybe a deep example from a company where a friend of mine is working, and they have this like huge multitonned presses, and they have I think like 10 iterations per second, and they need to see problems in the data really, really fast. Otherwise, the machine is broken beyond repair in under two or three seconds. They have like an oil pressure problem and if they have certain patterns in the oil pressure, then they need to shut down the machine. So this needs to happen in one or two seconds. Otherwise, yeah, the machine is broken beyond repair, and then the data quality issue is not the biggest problem.

00:51:48 Interviewer

Yeah, that's a good point. I guess that's also an example of the business interest conflict where, well, whatever the quality of the of your data is, you need to work fast, and you don't really have time to take care of it, or you have to do it very fast.

00:52:05 Speaker 3

I think, Speaker 4, you said this with the sensor drift before, right?

00:52:08 Speaker 4

Mm. (agrees)

00:52:09 Speaker 3

I think most drifts are only come before over a longer period of time, does it?

00:52:18 Speaker 4

Yes. So typically, there's I think Speaker 5 knows better. They have done some on drift detection, but I guess one of the main reasons is that the sensors degrade over time, probably.

00:52:34 Speaker 3

If you say over time, how long?

00:52:36 Speaker 4

That depends on the use case, of course.

00:52:40 Speaker 5

So for example, it's if some tools I don't know a saw is used for a longer time than you see how it degrades somehow. Then you can try to find, for example, when it would be best to like, repair it, or use another saw or something like that.

00:53:00 Interviewer

You can do predictive maintenance on the sensors for predictive maintenance.

00:53:04 Speaker 5

So this would be one use case.

00:53:06 Speaker 4

So the velocity that you mentioned with the real time I guess is one of the main issues with the real time that Speaker 3 mentioned, right? This would be the velocity. Related thing, so I'm currently also thinking about we had this in another paper talking about an anti-lock braking system. The ABS in the car. Where you have, usually. Redundant sensors not only one, but multiple that. If one fails, you have some fall back mechanisms. Of course, they have to do some real-time decision-making there and to handle the data quality issues. They have redundancy in place. And then also some fall-back mechanisms because this are really critical systems that are so safety here is definitely also affected by data quality issues. If you think about real-time systems, about cyber physical systems.

00:54:08 Speaker 5

I was thinking a bit about because we said, yeah, I mean, having so much data like in Group 1, volume, variety, velocity. This would be a problem for analysis later, right? But I

think that if the right knowledge is also attached to the data, maybe so what we are having in Group 4, maybe knowledge representation, stuff like that. It probably doesn't hurt so much to have a high amount of data because if you have the knowledge of what is really important from this data, then as Speaker 4 said, having this fall back mechanisms is only advantageous. So because why is it a problem that we have so much data because we can't really analyze it or maybe can't analyze it fast enough. Or don't know what is important, but I think if this data quality management is done right. Maybe then that isn't as big as an issue as it is, if you don't have the knowledge about the data.

00:55:17 Speaker 4

Or if you know how to process it efficiently, right?

00:55:19 Speaker 5

Or if you know how to process it, yeah.

00:55:21 Speaker 4

So you could do the edge processing then if you know how to do the edge processing on the high-volume data in order to derive what you need then this will solve the problem, for example, yes.

00:55:39 Speaker 5

But yeah, so. I think maybe for me this Group 4 would be quite important to have that information because you can then throw away the data, which is unnecessary, maybe and keep the data which you need and only analyze that which would give you probably a very big advantage. But I also think that Group 4 is the one which is missing most of the times. So this is, I think in many use cases, you don't have much information about this knowledge representation.

00:56:20 Speaker 4

But then there's throwing away that you mention also raises another issue because in some industries you need accountability or some kind of logging mechanism to store a lot of stored lots of data for very long time because of some, if something may happen in two years, you may want to trace back the cause. And then you have this issue that you

had some data quality issues in the past, but you had a challenge to keeping track of everything like.

00:56:49 Speaker 5

So what I mean is more like that you only record the parts of the data. So, for example, only when the machine produced the specific parts and not all the time during the day they hold it. But yeah, I agree. So you can't throw away anything.

00:57:05 Speaker 4

It would be in the aviation industry, for example, if you think about the big turbines. They produce a really, really lot of data and this needs to be stored for a very long time. To be reconsidered. And this storage of the data to ensure the data quality later on is, can be very challenging and costly.

00:57:28 Speaker 5

But I think also there probably they would be very happy to have like know which of the data is really important for the parts because they also don't want to save everything. Just. Because they don't know exactly what belongs to which part or something?

00:57:45 Speaker 2

Yeah. And also related to that is the provenance. Probably not just storing it, but also if this data is used to derive first data and abstracted, for example. Also keep in track of provenance of what led to what is a challenge, I guess. It needs to be taken care of.

00:58:09 Speaker 4

So, Interviewer, please interrupt us if it's if it's becoming too much or if it's... I'm not sure if this is helping. Kind of brainstorming about other things.

00:58:18 Interviewer

I think it's interesting. I thought I would let the ball roll for some time while you were all busy. I think it's also interesting the way you point how these things relate to each other. So, to some extent, if you can master Group 4 well, Group 1, Group 2 are less of a problem

like this issue if you solve it will also help in solving other issues, but at the same time, if these issues are both. Well, if you have a lot of high volume and you have no idea of what is relevant, then you have a bigger problem than if you have a low volume or if you know what is relevant. So I think the whole discussion was also interesting for us. And yeah, I'm not sure yet what conclusions we can draw from it, but there are definitely very nice inputs, so. Very happy.

00:59:16 Speaker 4

Speaker 5, I also have another question because this is something that we currently face is that we have a distributed system usually we have multiple sources collecting data, time stamping data as well, and then we have the issue that clocks might not be synced everywhere. Which might also introduce some data quality issues. How are you dealing with that?

00:59:43 Speaker 5

So what we do when we collect data we faced the same problem and we even have let's say different time stamps for the data we collect because one is the time stamp of the execution engine which is global, let's say. But the problem is between the like when you collected the data and when you receive it, you have all the network latency which can change a bit in between. And in the metadata we usually have the internal clock of the measurement. But I mean, they are not synchronized. So you would need to synchronize them with something so that you get this. For us usually it's good enough if we use the timestamp of the execution engine which is let's say a global timestamp.

01:00:38 Speaker 4

No, so this, this, this processing ingestion time processing and yeah, different semantics there that you can use. But also something that may cause. So I think the problem is again this is a distributed system. Which?

01:00:56 Speaker 5

I think it might cause, it causes these problems.

01:00:58 Speaker 4

Yeah. So, I guess again somehow goes to Group One because we have heterogeneity and distributed systems, usually in IoT that produce data. And with that comes a lot of data quality issues at the source already.

01:01:26 Interviewer

Some things I'm quite surprised that no one mentioned or mentioned yet was C7 and C8 because for us, it was initially the issue of ambiguity, which then we thought maybe we should split. Also discussing with Pilot interview speaker. And. We were thinking that you might have an opinion or an idea about that. But no one mentioned it yet, so. Do you like the idea of splitting what we called causality ambiguity? So when you have a specific issue that is showing your sensor data, it's not always obvious what the cause is. And C8, which is well, what then to solve it?

01:02:17 Speaker 2

So I speak for myself. My appreciation for this decision to split in two because indeed one thing is having the ambiguity at the source, and then you have its effect in a cascading manner. And the solution as well is becoming challenging then, these disambiguations. And this leads to the multiple possibilities also to interpret or to reach to a solution of disambiguate. A lot of which use cases you had in mind here, and I'd be interested in knowing about those indeed.

01:03:07 Interviewer

I think the example that I was mentioning was from a paper I had two years ago where I was reviewing the literature, trying to find some patterns between some issues in the sensors or in the system. The issue that it was causing in the sensor data and the issues that it was causing in an event log when you abstract the sensor data to get some activities or some events of your process. So I was trying to find some recurrent patterns in previous papers that were doing process mining with IoT and I found that sometimes the same cause could lead to multiple issues like some papers where they were working in the mining industry and there they had a very difficult environment, very hot, very wet, it made it difficult for the sensors to track to collect data correctly, and they had a lot of noise and outliers. And these noise and outliers were sometimes causing or could cause multiple issues in the log and in the sensor data. So it could be that they were not detecting the right activity because the pattern was not very clear, but it will also be that they were also using the sensor data to detect when a new process instance was starting based on a specific pattern, and if that pattern was not clear, well then they were not detecting that a new instance was starting, or they were detecting it or starting when it didn't. So there

we had multiple types of issues in the log based on the same cause, and you also had the same sort of effects that the same issue in your log could be due to multiple causes. So, that's where the idea came from that at first we thought we can derive some nice patterns, and then we found, actually, it's not so clear.

01:05:12 Speaker 2

You have also some links to C9 and C13 because that's where you employ procedures, and maybe you make use of knowledge to try to resolve these ambiguities.

01:05:26 Interviewer

That's true. Technically, if you were able to always perfectly identify the source and the sort of pattern, it should be quite easy to get the procedure but.

01:05:45 Speaker 2

As long as you have enough knowledge.

01:05:49 Interviewer

Yeah, if you do.

01:05:52 Interviewer

If you have no more ideas, we can maybe go back to the questions and check if more things come to mind because we discussed some challenges, some new challenges, like for instance the metadata here, or the knowledge about the environment. We mentioned some sort of heterogeneity here [speaker 5] mentioned that for him, these things were actually quite similar and stemming from the same well for different examples of the same kind of overarching.

01:06:51 Speaker 5

And so maybe I would because you had this. I would, you combine and split up some challenges and would at least try to for the different challenges, maybe if this leads to too much data, not enough data, incorrect data, or maybe for Group 2 that you don't know what's going on. Maybe this would be interesting, or I mean the challenges as you said

granularity can lead to multiple things, also, maybe this would be interesting. This is represented in the data, but maybe only for me.

01:07:30 Speaker 2

No, no, I agree to [Speaker 5] on that. Think it would be interesting to have this more explicit.

01:07:40 Interviewer

Yes. Then we also had the wait I'm forgetting. We also had the whole discussion about the timeliness of the detecting handling of the issues, how sometimes if you have to do it on the spot and if you're able to do it in real time, then some issues can vanish like C12. While some others are actually maybe easier to handle, if you have more time, like the volume and the velocity somehow, if you have more time, then you might be better able to solve it. If you have more compact knowledge representation, you might also be better able to deep the volume and with the velocity. Yeah. We also had a lot of nice examples and use cases from everyone, I think. Now I think what would be interesting, and what's a little bit touched upon by [speaker 5], but we would like to have something a little bit go a bit further in the discussion would be how would we order the challenges or the groups of challenges? From like the most important, most critical, most dangerous from the ones which might be less difficult to handle. For instance, which might impact the results less negatively. What are your thoughts?

01:09:43 Speaker 4

My clear thought on this is very clear. It depends. This is all, really.

01:09:51 Speaker 4

Very much related to use cases and interests. Yeah. So I would say I couldn't rank this reasonably without any context.

01:10:02 Speaker 2

And I think a possible strategy to work this out is use case dependent. Maybe to look at these dependencies or cascading effects of the issues, and then I try to trace back to what might be the origin for specific use case of most cascading issues. But I also do not have a definite answer on that.

01:10:32 Speaker 4

I think especially if you think about those, those effects that the different things might happen to each other. I think it's also a lot about trade-offs that you need to discuss what does the tradeoff that I'm willing to do for my specific use case or my business interest or whatever? I think this is really, and then it comes down to different stakeholder perspectives usually they have different aspects, I think there the group three could be really the driving factor when you discuss about how important for a specific use case is a specific challenge, then the Group 3 could be from my point, probably something that drives decisions and this ranking.

01:11:15 Speaker 2

But maybe a counterargument to that can be that in some cases I'm looking at privacy specifically. You may have no possibility of addressing that issue because maybe you have GDPR or whatever you need to be compliant with that, and you cannot. Do anything to fix this, and you need to live with the issue of having to respect privacy. But probably you meant that also when you talked about the trade-offs?

01:11:42 Speaker 4

For some you have more context like rules and regulations where you don't have any influence, and you need to comply and then you this is fixed with all the positive and negative consequences, and then you have all the other aspects that you can maybe fine tune. And try to find good trade-offs with one specific point.

01:12:05 Speaker 5

But I think maybe because also the things we discussed. So I think you described that you usually use some not so privacy. Interrupting sensors. And then sometimes you switch to ones which are interrupting the privacy more, and I think this would then probably also be some kind of data quality management, right? Because you have the knowledge that maybe you switch to something, or I also thought about what we said about the different timestamps maybe that for some use cases where you combine multiple sensors you need different timestamps. Then when you combine two time series, let's say of the same machine because then you can use the internal time, and it's much more precise because you use the internal thing and don't have network latency and stuff like that. So I think knowledge representation helps very much in tackling different problems here, and also I mean the whole Group 1, probably. So for me, Group 4 would be probably if you

want to analyze something, you could get the most out of it if you have a nice knowledge representation, maybe. I don't know if you agree. The others for me, I can't really rate them.

01:13:30 Speaker 3

I would say Group 2 is a bit more important than four because you first need the information that you can store and reuse and represent. Just from a like step-by-step approach.

01:13:50 Speaker 5

So you mean?

01:13:53 Speaker 3

I mean, you derive the data quality issues in Group 2 with like the new data quality issue C5 and so on and in Group 4 you represent the information you gathered from C5 and to C9. And all of them went whatever you do, and you're not a representation.

01:14:16 Speaker 5

I mean, is it really useful if you detect that this is a new data quality issue or a rare data quality issue if you don't know what to do with them then?

01:14:28 Speaker 3

No, but don't need to 1st detect the other words you cannot act. If you have more trigger than you can turn around a procedure against.

01:14:39 Speaker 2

But from what we discussed before, I would say that still the knowledge representation could also be what helps you to identify these issues.

01:14:53 Speaker 5

Maybe let's talk about what I understand in knowledge representation that for example I have. I know that for some sensors These new patterns apply, or they are more likely maybe to apply, and then I can look for them maybe more efficiently. This would for me be the knowledge representation, I think you are coming from the other way and saying. If you don't detect them in the first place, then there's no use having knowledge about them, which is also fair, but I think maybe the knowledge can also help in detecting it more efficiently or more easily. But.

01:15:37 Speaker 3

Yeah. Nice to see you confirming.

01:15:41 Speaker 4

So just to be sure that the message representation is really just how to represent the knowledge. It's not about having knowledge. So everything about knowing the data quality and so on is all Group 2, right?

01:15:55 Interviewer

Yeah, group 4 is really about how do you represent it in your system or in your knowledge base, OK?

01:16:00 Speaker 4

Yes, like [Author 3]'s ontology, for example. Who wants to have a technologist for everything?

01:16:06 Speaker 5

Yes, so this would be Group 4 or group.

01:16:10 Speaker 4

But is this data quality management work for this group. If you just talk about so, I think it's a bit confusing that you have group 2 called "Knowledge" and then Group 4 "Knowledge Representation". Might introduce some confusion, and I'm also not sure about the name of Group 4 if it is currently representing the two challenges.

01:16:46 Interviewer

Thing that we also discussed because. Yeah, it's difficult to find one term to encompass everything that you should see Group 2 as knowledge of the issues and four as more the representation of this knowledge. How do we? Yeah, stay with the stylist.

01:17:05 Speaker 4

At an overreaching transfer, but then reuse in does is not covered by the representation.

01:17:14 Interviewer

No, that's true. But 2 is about having the knowledge and 4 is about dealing with it somehow.

01:17:20 Speaker 4

Yeah, it's somewhat ending, yeah. So I would say Group 4 is not named nicely, and I'm not sure if the two things go well together in a group or not.

01:17:33 Speaker 5

It's OK, maybe a question are these different groups in, let's say, different steps of the process. So, could we say that Group 1 and Group 3 are more in the data collection process? Issues which happen in the data collection process and maybe two and four afterwards when analyzing them. Or so also question to the others or do you see them on like happening at the same time and occurring at the same time?

01:18:08 Interviewer

I would say Group 3 is not only about the data collection process because it's also about if you think about the business interest conflicts, it's also about how you organize your process which is a bit broader and which might have it before and after.

01:18:23 Speaker 5

OK. Let me rephrase that. You would fix it at the in the collection process, right? If you have issues there so like changing a sensor, you would change something in the collection process, right? Well, on the right side you would fix something in the analysis pipeline somehow.

01:18:46 Interviewer

I would say that C11 might also tell you instead of repairing the sensor, just apply the script in the analysis phase. It's more like an in the middle. Deciding where you should go, and I have the feeling that all this importance thing, you took a point of view, like a lot of more like practitioners, if we have a system, and we have these issues, what should we do first? Would be the most important in some use cases? But maybe you could try to think about it as a scientist. Which of these problems do you think is actually the hardest to solve? That's also something that's well in a. For us, it's interesting to have both perspectives, like what is in practice when you have, when you have a system running and you have these issues, what should you do first? But then it's also interesting to have an idea of what are actually the hardest problems to solve for us. You have other thoughts about that, or would you also say difficult, it depends on still?

01:20:26 Speaker 2

Now I see those challenges at different levels. So it's also difficult for me to say, OK, this specific one is more challenging than others because it's also difficult to compare due to the fact that they apply at different levels of granularity of a process, let's say from the collection to analysis to the management. Only if you ask me for these more interesting, I will tell you probably think Group 4 because I'd see it as linking back to what [speaker 5] I said before. Something quite important to try to solve challenges at the other levels.

01:21:13 Speaker 3

Maybe we can provide the most out of the hardest thing for the group. Did you define this by levels?

01:21:26 Speaker 4

Again, again, I think also from a scientific point of view, it depends on the area that working on. So, if recall correctly, our very nice BPM paper which made it into the biggest BPM challenges to solve before we die defined granularity. At least in the first group, if you talk about process mining and finding the right levels of granularity, this is always an issue.

But if you think about if you are a big data guy distributed systems guy, then probably something regarding the velocity and the volume is more is the hardest problem. I think it depends on the paper that you want to send, the conference that you want to send the paper to.

01:22:08 Interviewer

We are targeting a more process mining audience.

01:22:12 Speaker 4

Well, then, granularity, I think is, I would say is one of the biggest BPM problems to solve before we die.

01:22:19 Interviewer

It's in the paper.

01:22:34 Speaker 4

But in the end, it all comes down to, I would say, knowledge, it's about knowledge, if you have enough knowledge you can solve all the problems usually. But you do not have a perfect knowledge of everything that you need to know.

01:22:47 Interviewer

Yeah, you might have perfect knowledge. But then you have a new data quality issue.

01:22:53 Speaker 4

But they know about this. They have knowledge about this. Yes, they know about this.

01:22:55 Interviewer

Because you have the perfect knowledge. Yep.

01:22:58 Speaker 4

Know how to solve? You know where it comes from.

01:23:01 Speaker 5

And I also think. I mean, it's also depending on which fixes you want to apply. I mean, for big data, there's a very simple fix. Just throw everything away, that's too much? I mean, it's not the real fix, but then you don't have too much data, probably. And I think for other things, it's much harder, maybe. But yeah, I. I agree with Speaker 4 that it's very difficult to rank them by which one is the hardest to. Because they also have many interdependencies, in my opinion especially. As we discussed before.

01:23:46 Interviewer

OK, then, shall we say that it's it depends. It depends on a lot, and we've heard people saying Group 2 was the hardest. Three, Group 4, I don't think anyone said Group 1 was the hardest. But yeah, I guess someone would probably come up with the reason why it would be very difficult. Well, do you still think you could try to find the most difficult in each group, or is that also depending on and a bit meaningless. And we should skip and go to the last part of the discussion.

01:24:31 Speaker 4

So you should give us a context point. In what scope you think or like what area? Like BPM area and then this makes it a bit easier for us to judge. What is most relevant? Toughest one there?

01:24:51 Interviewer

OK. As a BPM guy who wants to get the best quality possible for your log for further process analysis. OK, what do you think? OK. If it's too difficult, it's also a valid output, I think, of the discussion.

01:25:43 Speaker 5

Yeah, I think maybe in Group 1, I would probably agree to granularity because when you go to different granularities, you also have less data obviously than usually so few. There are higher level things, than the other problems also.

01:26:06 Speaker 4

Yeah, as definitely as we have different levels of granularity from different sources, and you want to do a homogeneous analysis and then there you have one of the sensors was very, very detailed, and you can get the data from and then others are only one and two or whatever. Then the results of the analysis become messy. So to go finding a way to homogenize everything with all the properties that are coming before like volume, variety and velocity, to really consider everything and have the knowledge how to process it to get to achieve the red level at the same level of commonality. Why keep privacy interests and business interests? You know what? Everything somehow comes intertwined in the end.

Presentation of the mapping of challenges to DQ management steps

01:27:02 Interviewer

OK, then. I think we have tackled all these four questions quite thoroughly, and we can move to our last discussion point, which was about the well, what we call here, our data quality issue management cycle. The neighbors are apparently making all those noises. Hope you don't hear it. If I don't hear it. So we have here, as we discussed last time in, we came up with four main steps. This framework is much simpler than the one we discussed last time. Because, well, in this, we would like first to have one paper on the shorter paper discussing challenges and then, based on that, refine our framework further and work on it further. But here we have 4 main steps which were the detection, handling, so detection being when a new batch of data or a new case comes in other issues and if there are issues, which ones? Handling was about, then based on this issue, what kind of what should we do? Should we try to repair a sensor, replace a sensor, a script does some preprocessing, et cetera? Solving is about taking in this sort of list of possible solutions and prioritizing and applying them, and evaluations about checking whether the data is now clean and if the process is not repaired like if a sensor was repaired. Did it work? So it's mostly these four steps that we want to discuss here. Is it clear?

01:29:07 Speaker 4

Can you generalize this to the plan-do-check-act?

01:29:13 Interviewer

It's very similar.

01:29:15 Speaker 4

I think you should. If possible, you should align it with that. Or, if [author 3] is involved, he always likes MAPKE, so I think if you could phrase it along those lines, it's easier to put into this. To argue, this is how the cycle sounded.

01:29:30 Interviewer

OK. Yeah, that's also something that Pilot interview speaker had mentioned, actually. But yeah, I think they are very similar. And here it's mostly about, what we would mostly want is to discuss which of these steps each challenge affects most. So we have a proposed mapping. And we would like you basically to say whether you agree or whether you like to modify some things. So, for the volume, we thought it was mostly an issue about detection and handling because, well, the volume makes it more difficult to automatically process. All the data and to detect all potential data quality issues basically. And based on this, to propose some suitable solutions. And here you can shoot straight away after each challenge tell us if it's suitable or not according to you.

01:30:41 Speaker 4

So, then if I change the volume like for say, I want to have less data. Is that already related to solving? So if I manipulate the volume I can already also solve maybe an issue, or?

01:30:59 Interviewer

I'm not sure if I get your point because what we mean here is that typically it's more difficult to detect and to handle the challenges, well to detect and to handle the DQIs if you have more volume, all other things equal.

01:31:13 Speaker 4

Well. But then the problem is that you have too much data.

01:31:22 Speaker 2

Mm.

01:31:23 Speaker 4

Or data at a too high frequency. Then a solution regarding this would be just to reduce the data, if you know how, but then never mind so.

01:31:37 Interviewer

I think that would be some preprocessing, for me that would be part of what makes the handling and the detection difficult. Actually, that you might need to take extra steps.

01:31:48 Speaker 4

I was just wondering if it's already also related to the solving somehow.

01:31:56 Interviewer

I would say solving is about applying some solution like replacing the sensor. In that regard.

01:32:04 Speaker 4

Or reducing the volume.

01:32:09 Interviewer

Reducing the volume is not going to solve the DQI. I'm not saying well, the DQI here is not that we have too much data. Problem is that it's difficult to find the DQIs because of the volume.

01:32:19 Speaker 4

Yeah. OK. OK.

01:32:24 Interviewer

We will have other, well, there are challenges where it might be relevant later. So, no objection to this proposal. Then we had basically the same kind of problems for a variety and the same kind of conclusion that variety makes it especially more difficult to detect

the DQIs and to handle them. Because if you have different types of data, it might be more difficult to find a suitable solution. But that the rest should be, well, less impacted. Is that also? Something we can agree on.

01:33:16 Speaker 3

Do you reuse some of the information evaluation step?

01:33:25 Interviewer

In what sense?

01:33:29 Speaker 3

I know that you said you just considered, for example, the volume in regard to finding the DQIs. But when you have the DQIs and you evaluate, does the volume also make a difference on the variety of the data? Do you compare against the real data in any or plan to do?

01:33:56 Interviewer

You should, yeah.

01:33:59 Speaker 3

So then maybe it also affects the evaluation phase.

01:34:06 Interviewer

OK.

01:34:09 Speaker 2

I think I agree. But then also the application of the solution could be, well, the development and the application of the solution could be made more challenging by the variety.

01:34:30 Speaker 3

You. Maybe it also makes more sense to await the challenges or the effects of the challenge because if you have less DQIs that you find in the detection phase because you have less volume. Then it also affects the solving because the solving has less information to deduct from.

01:34:53 Speaker 3

So maybe it's more like, it affects mainly the detection, but also the later stages.

01:35:01 Interviewer

Maybe some extra input here: Our reasoning to focus on detection and handling for these challenges was that. Basically, if you're able to detect the DQIs in such a large volume of data, and/or such a high variety of data, then the solving in the evaluation will not be as challenging because they would. Well, if you have a way to handle the volume during detection and handling, then you will also not have a big problem for solving and for evaluation. For instance. Hopefully, you will now detect the DQIs in all the data. So that when you go to this, but it's solving into these evaluation steps, you will not have the full data sets, but only a fraction of it where there were DQIs where you need to apply some techniques or repair some sensors and then re-evaluate by comparing the clean log with the original log. So that's OK, the volume also somehow impacts the solving and evaluation, but the biggest issues are the detection and handling phase.

01:36:24 Speaker 2

So, maybe here you already considered that, but why not having something other than a binary entry in this table?

01:36:38 Interviewer

Well, we could have. We could have a more refined view now we saw was checking. The most impacted steps. You could take. You could, of course, say that every challenge impacts every step, more or less. But here the idea is which ones are the most impacted and which ones will.

01:37:05 Interviewer

Which steps will be the most difficult? Because you can suggest having, like a one and then a 0.5 or something like that, if that's what you mean. Or a + -, A plus and minus.

01:37:22 Speaker 2

Yeah, yeah. Something in these lines. Yeah. However, you like to be represented, yeah.

01:37:25 Speaker 3

They probably only have the same problem, right? 0.5 and not 0.2. I think you cannot, exactly. Or the distribution about all these four parts will be.

01:37:44 Speaker 2

Maybe what is important, at least for me here, would be to have some argument. Supporting the presentation of these roles in the table. This could help us too. Understandable. Then agree or criticize. Your choice.

01:38:08 Interviewer

Yep. So as I said, the idea is that the volume will be the biggest issue for detection and handling because well at later stages you will hopefully already have reduced this volume to some extent. Because you will not detect DQIs in all the chunks of data to analyze, but only in some of them, which will make it easier than to solve into evaluate. On this reduced data set. And some of, well, not all the solutions in solving will also be really impacted by the volume. If you just have to repair a sensor or to replace a sensor, then it's somehow. Irrespective of the volume of data that the sensor generates. So that's why we were arguing that detection and handling were the most critical steps for the volume.

01:39:02 Speaker 3

Mm.

01:39:11 Interviewer

So, is it something you can now agree on, or are you still a bit doubtful? Keeping in mind that we also mean to cross only the ones which are the most impacted.

01:39:36 Speaker 2

I think I can agree with you. Perhaps the methodologically, you could still proceed in the next lines to give a brief support to yours.

01:39:48 Interviewer

That's what I was planning on. Sorry if the first one was a bit unclear. That's all right. So then for the velocity here we were thinking mostly of detection because the velocity is well, the issue there is that you get a lot of data very fast. But, so, the detection will have to happen very fast as well, probably in real time. After that, if you have detected things in real time, then the handling, solving and evaluation might well be easier or be less impacted by this because then the same kind of handling solving and evaluation might be applied then if you didn't have data coming very fast. Is that also something OK for you?

01:40:51 Speaker 3

If you have the execution in the handling phase. Or if you have the handling phase, is it time-critical? Is it a long-running part of the process?

01:41:09 Interviewer

I think here with velocity we were thinking mostly about how fast data was coming in and not necessarily about how fast the process or the log had to be repaired, so it's mostly about can we handle all the data coming in very fast and analyze all data coming in and not about can we repair it very fast?

01:41:35 Speaker 2

OK.

01:41:36 Interviewer

So, that's something that we discussed earlier, actually.

01:41:44 Interviewer

It might also be an issue if you consider that your process is time-critical and you have to get the correct data very fast. I don't know, in healthcare, you might have some processes where things have to happen very fast or in production environments. But I would see that

as another issue than the velocity of the data. Then we move to granularity. Where there we have, we thought it was mostly a problem for detection and handling again. So mostly about can we get the data to the right granularity level to detect the issues and to handle them, well, propose the right solutions and then well, once you have data at the right granularity level, it will be quite easy to solve and evaluate the solutions. So it's a bit, the same line of reasoning as for the previous ones. Then we go to Group 2 with the new data quality issues. Here we think it will be difficult at each step because first you have to detect something which you have never seen before. You have to find a new solution and apply it, and you have to evaluate it without necessarily knowing exactly. What the data would look like without the data quality issue? So we think for each step it would be difficult. For the rare data quality issues here we focused more on the detection because typically, it's well the issue there is that you don't see them very often and you might not. Your system might have a harder time detecting them, but once they are detected, typically you should have already some potential solutions existing, like the solutions that were applied before in this first stage. And you should already have a better idea, OK.

01:43:50 Speaker 5

I mean, for C6, if you only have the data quality issues very rarely, couldn't it be that you only have a very limited set of handling and solving things. So, it could be that probably depends on how rare it is. If it's very rare. Probably, I would argue that handling and solving would also be maybe a thing like for the new data. But I, I'm fine with it because yeah, it should be different from the new.

01:44:27 Speaker 3

If you have a rare issue, then it occurred before, so it should be easier to detect it, right?

01:44:35 Interviewer

It will be easier to detect than a new one. It will still be more difficult than if it's one which you encounter more frequently because you might have fewer examples of it. It will be more difficult to determine whether it's that issue or another one or no issue.

01:44:55 Speaker 5

OK.

01:44:55 Interviewer

That's the reasoning now. The rare data quality issue, what we intend with it is, it could be the second time you see it, it could be, maybe the 10th time. So you could perhaps argue that there might be a small distinction between really the second time or the 10th time.

01:45:21 Interviewer 2

Yeah.

01:45:21 Interviewer

That's how we represent it for now.

01:45:25 Speaker 3

For me, it's hard to distinguish rare issues and like it's also a known issue. You have some data stored about it, some knowledge about it. So for me, it's not straightforward to think that detection is harder than something that I already encountered. For me, it would be harder to say if I have like what should I do if it occurs because. I did not see it so often.

01:45:55 Interviewer

OK.

01:45:57 Speaker 3

Like for example, a really dumb example of mine. If my front door was broken. That's a really rare issue, but I have no idea what I should do then. But it's pretty straightforward to identify.

01:46:13 Interviewer

OK. I think I see your reasoning. OK. Then for the ambiguity. Yeah, I think I can pick them both at the same time. There, I think we kept the same mapping then when we only had one type of ambiguity and there we want to, we wanted to say OK, if you are not sure what kind of issue it is well that's going to be difficult to detect, then it's going to be difficult to suggest a solution to apply it and to check whether the solution has worked. Because, well, your data might look different, might seem better, but you might have solved the

wrong issue. And you might have data which in the end seems better, but is not. We give everything for causality and solution. You could also perhaps argue that there should be a distinction between them. Yeah, let us know your thoughts.

01:47:32 Speaker 2

I think I agree with this identification, with this mapping. Because you could have ambiguity that carries along until the evaluation, and potentially even after that, you're still not sure.

01:47:53 Speaker 3

Yep.

01:47:56 Speaker 5

Sure.

01:47:59 Interviewer

OK, by the way. We're not going to modify it now anyway, but that doesn't mean that we are not taking your feedback into account. Like [speaker 3], when I was discussing C6. We're going to discuss internally and see what we modify. But your feedback will be taken into account.

01:48:26 Speaker 5

Maybe to C6 if your door is broken you also won't detect it if you only have a sensor which says your door is open. Yeah.

01:48:37 Speaker 3

So it's not valid for all examples.

01:48:42 Speaker 4

So I was wondering for C7 and C8, what happens if you agree with the detection and what if you can fix the ambiguity issue in the detection? Then all the others do not matter anymore.

01:49:02 Interviewer

Yeah, but I think the thing here is that you're not certain that you fixed it.

01:49:10 Speaker 4

Then this cascades, yes.

01:49:12 Interviewer

Yeah, that's well, whether you have identified the right cause or not. The problem is that you are not sure about it. And that there is still some uncertainty and ambiguity which makes the rest of the process a bit doubtful. It's again, if you have perfect knowledge, of course, nothing here is really impacted and if you can solve this then typically the rest will also be easier to solve. Also, why I think you see more crosses around detection is because usually this is pretty critical and if you don't detect the right issue all the rest won't work.

01:50:02 Speaker 4

No, because quality is of course poor detection. You should know.

01:50:08 Interviewer

Yeah. Even when you have detected a problem, it's still not always straightforward to solve it. But if you don't detect it, yeah.

01:50:17 Speaker 4

What was the difference between handling and solving? Sorry.

01:50:21 Interviewer

Handling is about suggesting some solutions and solving about deciding which one to apply and effectively applying them. OK.

01:50:33 Interviewer 2

OK, I need to interrupt. I need to leave. I was quiet until now because I was taking notes and [Interviewer] was leading it. So thank you all for your participation, and I'm excited to hear what you thought about the other challenges. Thank you very much and see you hopefully soon. Bye.

01:50:53 Interviewer

Thanks [interviewer 2].

01:50:53 Speaker 2

Bye.

01:50:54 Speaker 3

All right. Bye.

01:50:57 Interviewer

OK. It's almost time. So let's get to the last slide and wrap it up. So, for the procedure refinement, it's about updating. Well, updating the system. Here we thought that it was also kind of important for every step. Because you might have to update the detection. For instance, you might have to update the detection if you have a new issue or if you classified the previous issue incorrectly. You might have to update the handling and the solving with some potential new solutions. Or change the order in which they should be applied and, of course, for evaluation, you first have to detect that your procedure has to be updated, and you have to make sure that it happened correctly. So that was the reasoning. Then for privacy, we were focusing on the handling and on the evaluation.

01:52:29 Speaker 4

Why not detection? Not the detection?

01:52:32 Speaker 3

Yeah, same question.

01:52:34 Interviewer

I think our reasoning was that the sharing data would mostly help in providing potential solutions to known DQIs. But it's true that if data sets or information shared also gives you examples of DQIs which...

01:53:01 Speaker 3

The notes from.

01:53:02 Interviewer

So, here the idea was mostly about handling an evaluation because you can more easily check if something worked by comparing it with other data sets and with other experiences and handling because it might give you. Ideas of solutions? Though, indeed, why not. You could also have examples of DQIs you have never seen. In on your production line or in your organization in another data set which might also help you.

01:53:42 Speaker 4

So maybe you are assuming that all the regulations that lead to some privacy issues might be known, and then it's more about. Yeah. Handling those by being aware would be that that was like GDPR. Is. And you know that. You can detect easily if it's violated or not. And maybe that was your reasoning for saying OK, detection might be not that important.

01:54:10 Speaker 2

But yeah.

01:54:13 Speaker 5

I would maybe, I mean, I agree with the detection, but I would argue that maybe it would be more solving than handling. Maybe in this case because I think you said that solving would be then choosing one of the solutions and maybe there would be some very privacy related things about how experienced the worker is, how fast the worker is. Usually when

you want to select from the things which get, so, like proposed in the handling. So maybe I would switch from handling to solving, but it depends on what you see as handling and solving, obviously.

01:54:55 Interviewer

OK. I think this mapping also came from the discussion with [Pilot interview speaker] and he probably had a very good reason.

01:55:10 Speaker 5

He always says that, but yeah.

01:55:13 Interviewer

He somehow convinced us but probably his reasoning was a bit intricate. I didn't remember it.

01:55:36 Speaker 5

But I mean, I mean you can check afterward and see if the reasoning is valid, which I had, or fits together with the other one.

01:55:47 Interviewer

Yep. OK. Then for C11, we thought that it was impacting everything. Because basically here, the problem is: Do you want to act upon some issues and do you actually care about them? So, do you want to actually replace your sensor? Do you shift the order in which you would apply these solutions by saying no, replacing a sensor is too costly or takes too long? So just apply some script instead. And the yeah, the evaluation by saying, OK, we might have to update the system, for instance. But we don't for these reasons.

01:56:47 Speaker 5

I think probably evaluation is the weakest one of these 4.

01:56:51 Interviewer

OK.

01:56:51 Speaker 5

Because I don't know. I mean, if there is a business decision that you don't have a sensor, and you can't evaluate, then I mean, of course. Yeah, probably that series. Yeah, it's OK for me.

01:57:09 Speaker 3

I don't really get the detection. Why? Why C11 detection or so? It's caused.

01:57:20 Interviewer

Yeah, I think I see your point that you would still detect the issues, but just decide not to do anything about them.

01:57:29 Speaker 3

No.

01:57:33 Interviewer

Yeah, that's a fair point.

01:57:34 Speaker 3

I mean, for handling and solving it makes sense.

01:57:37 Speaker 3

First, there's the business decision.

01:57:41 Speaker 5

Well, yeah. But I mean, if you say you don't like to replace the sensor, and it provides faulty values, then also detection is difficult, right?

01:57:54 Interviewer

Yeah, you're right.

01:57:54 Speaker 3

You can argue that, but for me, you still detect the error but just in the handling stage or in the solving stage say it's not important.

01:58:05 Interviewer

You could say that not replacing it for instance, makes it also more likely for other DQIs to occur, which might then make detection more difficult. In some way.

01:58:20 Speaker 3

Definitely to detect them because they can be from other sources.

01:58:29 Interviewer

I mean, the thing that the sensor is faulty or uncalibrated or something which might just make it more difficult to detect any issue and not only the ones which you are used to, but you might have even more issues occurring or it might make it more difficult to correlate with other sensors to detect other issues because of that decision. So yeah, but I see your point that detection is also a bit weak here, and that your reasoning could also make sense. OK. Then we had the data quality issue C12 where here we focused on the detection and handling in the sense that it's also a situation where you might detect a problem and then have to think, should we actually solve it and if you detect. If you have a data quality issue causing another one. And you remove the cause. It might also make it more difficult to identify the cause of the second problem. So this cascade where you remove the antecedent. So that was our reasoning.

01:59:55 Speaker 3

Wouldn't it be also hard in the evaluation phase to distinguish between a cascading effect and a non cascading effect?

01:59:55 Interviewer

Oh, it could be.

02:00:15 Speaker 3

And what? What exactly is the reasoning that you think in solving it's not that hard.

02:00:23 Interviewer

Well, it's not because you have one data quality issue that might be causing other problems that it's more difficult to solve it. Or that's more difficult, necessary to solve the other one. The issue with handling so proposing solutions but applying them will not be harder.

02:00:46 Speaker 3

No, can make sense.

02:00:51 Interviewer

Then we had the knowledge representation where there we thought, well, it impacts everything. If your knowledge representation is not straightforward and not correct, it will be more difficult to detect the issues. Will be more difficult to handle. Then it will be more difficult to apply the right solutions, and it will be more difficult to evaluate them. I think this is, yeah. Straightforward. And then we had the last one, which was about reuse and transfer of knowledge, where there we thought the main problems were about handling and solving. In the sense that we saw knowledge we use and transfer mostly about people on the work floor or data engineers who have to actually clean the data. Or repair the sensors that they are the people who have the knowledge about how to solve the issues. And this transfer and this reuse was mostly impacting the handling and the solving.

02:01:58 Interviewer 2

Hmm.

02:02:10 Speaker 2

So we assume that this is not knowledge used for detection.

02:02:16 Interviewer

We assume that it's mostly about handling and solving. Yeah. I think I see your point that, again, it could also be like the detection if it's about reusing and transferring knowledge about detecting the issues. Yeah, I think here the main issue is that we have to define C14 pretty clearly, but depending on this definition we might add it or not.

02:02:50 Speaker 2

Mm. Yeah. OK.

02:02:57 Interviewer

OK. No other comments on this? Or on anything else?

02:03:08 Speaker 3

Not for me.

[Closing and Farewell]